

3.35 (1H, m, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.95 and 4.3 (1H_A, dd, J 12, 5 Hz and H_B, dd, J 12, 2 Hz, of $-\text{O}-\text{C}(\text{H}_A)-\text{CH}(\text{H}_B)-\text{CH}_2$), 6.1 (1H, s, proton at position-3), 6.8 (1H, s, at position-5) and 7.3–7.55 (2H, m, proton at position-7 and -8).

4-Methyl-7-(2-hydroxy-3-isopropylaminopropoxy) coumarin (3): A mixture of 4-methyl-7-(2,3-epoxypropoxy)coumarin (1.0 g) and isopropylamine (1 ml) in methanol was refluxed for 6 h on a steam-bath. The solvent was then evaporated to afford 3 which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, (0.8 g), m.p. 140°; δ 1.1 (6H, d, $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3 , at position-4), 2.55–2.95 (5H, m, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHOH}$), 4.0 (2H, d of ArOCH_2), 6.21 (1H, s, proton at position-3) and 7.0–7.8 (3H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. S. Lele and S. S. Madhava Rao for the microanalysis and nmr spectra.

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Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo/H-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-arylpurimidines

M. D. ANKHIWALA

Department of Chemistry, R. R. Mehta College of Science, Palanpur-385 002

Manuscript received 24 December 1988, revised 10 March 1989, accepted 31 March 1989

2-AMINOPYRIMIDINES¹ are known for their physiological importance. With a view to get better therapeutic activity, some new 2-aminopyrimidines (2) were synthesised and evaluated for their antimicrobial activity. The compounds have been prepared² by the reaction of 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1) with guanidine nitrate in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide (40%) in ethanol (Scheme 1). Previously reported 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones³ and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones⁴ have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-butoxy-5-nitroacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-4-n-butoxy-5-

nitroacetophenone and various araldehydes and evaluated their biological activity^{3,4}. The structure of the compounds has been supported by elemental analysis and ir spectral data. The products have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate agar diffusion method⁵. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 μg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*. The compounds showed only mild antibacterial activity (inhibition 20–30%). The compounds 2 having bromo and chloro substituents in benzene ring were found to be more active. Maximum activity was observed in compounds (2) when R = 4-tolyl, 2- and 4-chlorophenyl, 2,4-dichlorophenyl against *S. aureus* and 2- and 4-bromophenyl, 4-methoxyphenyl against *E. coli*. The activity was not comparable with the known antibiotic like chloromycetin under similar condition. The most antifungal active compound of the series was Sl. no. 1 (Table 1); it inhibited the growth of *A. niger* to the extent of 80%. Most of the compounds showed moderate antifungal activity (inhibition 60–75%) and a few showed weak activity (inhibition < 55%) against *A. niger*. In general, the presence of chlorine atom in R decreased fungitoxicity.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AMINO-4,6-DIARYLPYRIMIDINES (2)^a

Sl. no.	R	X	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	205	70
2.	2'-Chlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl	190	75
3.	4'-Chlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl	240	78
4.	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl ₂	260	85
5.	4'-Methylphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ Br	185	65
6.	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₄ Br	162	70
7.	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₄ Br	155	65
8.	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₄ Br	180	70
9.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	135	65
10.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	201	60
11.	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	Br	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ Br	210	62
12.	Phenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	190	70
13.	2'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	235	75
14.	4'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	250	80
15.	2'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	202	85
16.	4'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	231	80
17.	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	270	90
18.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₄	185	70
19.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₄	208	65
20.	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	160	68
21.	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₄	175	70
22.	4'-Methylphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄	198	75
23.	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₄	217	70
24.	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅	165	60

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

(KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (2): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; X=Br; 1.00 g) and guanidine nitrate (0.30 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (40%, 5 ml) added to it portionwise during 3 h. The reflux was continued further for 6 h and the resulting solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from aqueous DMF, (70%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 52.17; H, 4.21; N, 12.12. C₂₀H₁₉O₄N₄Br calcd. for: C, 52.29; H, 4.14; N, 12.20%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 460, 3 330 (NH), 1 630 (C=N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic).

Similarly, other pyrimidines (Table 1) were prepared.

2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-H-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (2): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-4-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; X=H, 1.00 g) and guanidine nitrate (0.30 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (40%; 5 ml) added to it portionwise during 3 h. The reflux was continued further for 8 h and the resulting yellow solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from aqueous DMF, (75%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 63.20; H, 5.12; N, 14.82. C₂₀H₂₀O₄N₄ calcd. for: C, 63.16; H, 5.26;

N, 14.74%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 455, 3 335 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic).

Similarly, other pyrimidines (Table 1) were prepared.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the authorities of R. R. Mehta College of Science, Palanpur, for facilities.

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Pyrimidine Antagonists. Part-III. Synthesis of some 2,4-Diamino-5-substituted-phenylazo-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines and Evaluation of their Anticancer Property against Leukemia P388

(Miss) MAITREYEE DEBI

Department of Chemical Technology, University Colleges of Science and Technology, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 24 April 1986, revised 30 January 1989, accepted 31 March 1989

PURINE and pyrimidine possess widerange biological activities¹.

The presence of amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions of the pyrimidine ring and also the presence of hydroxyl and/or amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions having a bulky substituted-amino group in C-6 position² have been found to exhibit activity against *Streptococcus faecalis* ATCC 8043. The present investigation aims to keep the 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety intact and then substitute new group at the phenylmoiety at the C-6 position having phenylazo group in C-5 position.

In previous communications³ the present author reported the synthesis of some 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines and 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-amino-5-arylazopyrimidines.

³Present address: Civil Engineering Department, National Test House, 11/1 Judges Court Road, Calcutta-700 027.